

(100 mg; R_f 16.6 min). Fraction-3 on prep.-tlc (C_6H_6 - CH_2Cl_2 - Et_2O , 4.5 : 4.5 : 1) yielded 3,8-dihydroxypentadeca-1,9,14-trien-4,6-diyne (6 mg), *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid (14 mg) and a complex mixture of diterpene lactones. The latter was treated with CH_2N and separated by hplc ($MeOH-H_2O$, 9 : 1) giving 15-methoxy-16-oxo-15,16*H*-strictic acid methyl ester (20 mg; R_t 6.6 min), 15-methoxy-16-oxo-15,16*H*-hardwickiic acid methyl ester (30 mg; R_t 7.0 min), 15-methoxy-16-oxonidoresedic acid methyl ester (16 mg; R_t 7.2 min), methyl *nor*-strictiate (24 mg; R_t 7.9 min), methyl *nor*-hardwickiate (10 mg; R_t 9.4 min) and methyl-2 α -acetoxyhardwickiate (42 mg; R_t 12.4 min). Fraction-4 separated on tlc (C_6H_6 - CH_2Cl_2 - Et_2O , 1 : 1 : 1) yielded 5,3'-dihydroxy-3,6,7,4',5'-pentamethoxyflavone (130 mg; R_f 0.33), 16-oxo-15,16*H*-hardwickiic acid (12 mg; R_f 0.35), 15-methoxy-16-oxo-15,16*H*-strictic acid (20 mg; R_f 0.30), (-)auranamide (1, 14 mg; R_f 0.40) and 5-hydroxy-3,6,7,3',4',5'-hexamethoxyflavone (40 mg; R_f 0.42).

Ir spectra ($CHCl_3$) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer, 1H nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) on a Bruker WM400 (400 MHz) spectrometer and mass spectra on a Varian MAT 711 (70 eV) instrument.

Results and Discussion

Auranamide (1) was obtained as a colourless solid, m.p. 203–04°, $C_{18}H_{16}O_7N_2$, $[M^+]$ 506.2200 $[\alpha]_D^{25} -35^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$ 0.05).

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Its ir spectrum displayed strong carbonyl bands at 1740 (COOR), 140 (CONH) and 1600 cm^{-1} . The 1H nmr spectrum (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) was in agreement with the reported data². The mass fragmentation pattern was identical to that reported for auranamide². The identity of physical and spectroscopical properties established that our compound was auranamide (1). Since the rotation was negative and similar to that reported for auranamide the configuration at both chiral centres was *S* as established earlier by the synthesis of auranamide².

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Fruit Constituents of *Physalis minima* var. *indica* and One-step Conversion of Physalin B to 6-Epiphysalin G Acetate

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IN continuation of our search for withasteroids from *Physalis* species¹⁻³, we now report the chemical constituents of the fruits of *Physalis minima* var. *indica*, an annual weed of this region which differs from *Physalis minima* mainly by its more glabrescent leaves and distinctly five-angular fruiting calyx⁴.

Column chromatography of the petroleum ether extract of the fruits of *P. minima* var. *indica* resulted in the isolation of two constituents. The first constituent crystallised from benzene as pale yellow needles, m.p. 173°, and analysed for the molecular formula, $C_{18}H_{16}O_7$ (M^+ , m/z 344). It was recognised to be a flavonol from its uv spectral characteristics (vide Experimental). Its 1H nmr spectrum showed the presence of two *meta*-coupled aromatic hydrogens (δ 6.35 and 6.45, 1H, d, J 2 Hz each), a 1,2,4-trisubstituted-phenyl nucleus (δ 6.95, 1H, d, J 9.1 Hz; 7.73, 1H, dd, J 9.1, 2.2 Hz; 7.64, 1H, d, J 2.2 Hz) and three methoxyl groups (δ 3.87, 6H, s; 3.99, 3H, s). The compound gave a crystalline diacetate, m.p. 172–74°, whose 1H nmr spectrum showed additionally two 3H singlets at δ 2.35 and 2.45 for two acetoxy groupings. The data suggested the isolated flavonol to be a trimethyl ether of quercetin. The locations of the methoxyl groups in the flavone nucleus were considered to be 3, 7 and 4' from its uv spectral behaviour (vide Experimental) in presence of diagnostic shift

reagents and confirmed by establishing its identity with 3,7,4'-tri-*O*-methylquercetin⁶, prepared by selective methylation of quercetin⁶. This is the first report of the isolation of 3,7,4'-tri-*O*-methylquercetin from this plant.

The second eluted compound was identified, from its physical and spectral properties, as the withasteroid physalin B (1), previously reported from the aerial parts of this plant³. In order to provide additional chemical evidence in support of the 2,5-dien-1-one system present in physalin B, a solution of physalin B in glacial acetic acid was refluxed with mercuric acetate^{8,7} which, on usual work-up, yielded a compound, m.p. 260°. It was proved to be the 6 β -epimer of physalin G acetate (2, R= β -OAc) from an analysis of its various spectral data discussed in the sequel.

The compound showed a very small molecular ion peak at m/z 568 and a base peak at m/z 503, presumably formed by the elimination of a molecule of acetic acid. Its uv absorption maxima at 308 and 228 nm clearly indicated the presence of a steroidal 2,4-dien-1-one chromophore⁸. ^1H nmr spectrum of the compound showed four methyl singlets at δ 1.29, 1.41, 1.96 and 2.06 respectively, for 28-, 19-, 21- and acetoxy methyls. The olefinic region of the spectrum showed a double doublet at δ 6.85 (1H, dd, J 9.6, 6 Hz) and two doublets at δ 6.26 (1H, d, J 6 Hz) and 5.97 (1H, d, J 9.6 Hz) respectively, for H-3, H-4 and H-2 of a steroidal 2,4-dienone. A narrow triplet ($J \approx 3$ Hz) discernible at δ 5.57 was assigned to the carbinyl hydrogen at C-6 bearing an acetoxy function and the double doublet at δ 4.51 (1H, dd, J 13.4, 5.6 Hz) and the doublet at δ 3.78 (1H, d, J 13.4 Hz) were assigned to the geminally coupled oxymethylene at C-27. The chemical shift of the 19-methyl signal [δ 1.41 in place of δ 1.22 in physalin G (2, R= α -OH)] pointed to the β -orientation of the acetoxy function at C-6 position⁸. A comparison of the cd spectrum of physalin G (2, R= α -OH) with that of the derived 6-epiphysalin G acetate (2, R= β -OAc) showed a difference only in the sign of Cotton effect around 240 nm; the sign has been reported as positive⁹ for physalin G but found to be negative for the latter compound. It is interes-

ting to note that 6-epiphysalin G (2, R= β -OH) was prepared by Row *et al.*⁹ by treatment of physalin I (3) with acetic anhydride and pyridine at 100° for 3 h, a condition which is expected to furnish the corresponding acetate, same as that obtained by us from physalin B. The resistance to acetylation by 6-epiphysalin G explains why a rather drastic condition⁷ becomes necessary for the conversion of physalin B to 2 (R= β -OAc).

Experimental

Fruits of *P. minima* var. *indica* were collected from the campus of Banaras Hindu University during the month of September, 1988. The air-dried and powdered fruits (0.2 kg) were exhaustively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and the concentrated extract was chromatographed over silica gel, eluting with solvents of increasing polarity. Early fractions of benzene eluate yielded quercetin trimethyl ether (50 mg) and the later fractions furnished physalin B (22 mg), m.p. 265–70° (lit.¹⁰ 272°), identical with the sample isolated from the aerial parts of the plant³.

3,7,4'-Tri-*O*-methyl quercetin: It had m.p. 173° (lit.⁶ 172–73°); λ_{max} (MeOH) 353, 254 and 204 nm; λ_{max} (MeOH+NaOAc) 352, 255 and 214 nm; λ_{max} (MeOH+AlCl₃) 361, 268 and 212 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400, 1 660 and 1 610 cm^{-1} ; m/z 344, 343, 326, 301, 286, 258, 243, 217, 167, 158 and 135. The compound was indistinguishable (m.p., ^1H nmr, co-tlc) from quercetin trimethyl ether, prepared by selective methylation⁶ of quercetin.

Transformation of physalin B (1) to 6-epiphysalin G acetate (2, R= β -OAc): To a solution of physalin B (0.15 g) in glacial acetic acid (14 ml) was added $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ (0.3 g) and the mixture was refluxed for 12 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, filtered from the inorganics and the filtrate was freed from AcOH in a rotary vacuum evaporator. The residue was warmed with EtOAc and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated and chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with C_6H_6 -EtOAc (9 : 1) yielded a homogeneous solid (57 mg) which was crystallised from C_6H_6 as a microcrystalline solid of 6-epiphysalin G acetate (2, R= β -OAc) cd (dioxane) nm ($\Delta\epsilon$) 380 (+1.52), 310 (–2.02), 242 (–1.33) and 218 (+1.29).

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Studies on Diphenyl Sulphones. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of *p,p'*-Bis(2-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)diphenyl Sulphones and *p,p'*-Bis(3-chloro-4-aryl-2-azetidinon-1-ylaminocarbonyl)-diphenylsulphones

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SOME 2,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives possess wide spectrum of biological properties¹. Several new such derivatives (4) have been synthesised with a view to obtaining better therapeutic agents. A large number of antibiotics contain β -lactam heterocyclic moiety². Sulphones are reported to possess important therapeutic properties³. We have combined the two structures and synthesised some new 2-azetidinone derivatives.

p,p'-Dicarboxydiphenyl sulphone (1) was esterified with absolute ethanol and subsequently condensed with hydrazine hydrate to get *p,p'*-dihydrazinocarbonyldiphenyl sulphone (3). The hydrazide (3) on condensation with different aromatic acids in presence of phosphorous oxychloride gave (Scheme 1) the *p,p'*-bis(2-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)-diphenyl sulphones (4). The hydrazide (3) on condensation with different aromatic aldehydes gave the Schiff base (5), which on treatment with chloroacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine gave *p,p'*-bis(3-chloro-4-aryl-2-azetidinon-1-ylaminocarbonyl)diphenylsulphones (6). The compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

The antimicrobial screening of the oxadiazole and 2-azetidinon derivatives was carried out using cup-plate method⁴ at a concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. citrus*, *Pseudomonas fluores*, *Escherichia coli* and fungi *Aspergillus flavus* and *Candida albicans*.

The 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives (3) showed good activity against *P. fluores* and *C. albicans*, and moderately active against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *S. citrus* and *A. flavus*. The maximum activity was observed in the derivatives when R=2- and 3-aminophenyl against *P. fluores*, and R=3-chlorophenyl and 2-hydroxy-3-naphthyl against *C. albicans*.

Most of the 2-azetidinone derivatives (6) were moderately active against different strains of bacteria and fungi. The maximum activity was observed in the derivatives when R=4-chlorophenyl, 2,4-dichlorophenyl, and 4-hydroxyphenyl against *P. fluores*, and when R=2- and 4-methoxyphenyl against *C. albicans*.

Experimental

Mps. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analysis and spectral data. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a XL-100A (100.1 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

p,p'-Dicarbethoxydiphenyl sulphone (2): A mixture of *p,p'*-dicarboxydiphenyl sulphone (61.2 g, 0.2 mol), absolute ethanol (200 ml) and sulphuric acid (5.4 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The excess ethanol was then distilled off and the residue poured onto crushed ice. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (47.1 g, 65%), m.p. 159° (Found: S, 8.3. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6\text{S}$ requires: S, 8.4%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 150 and 1 330 cm^{-1} (S=O asym. and sym.), 1 725 (C=O), 2 940 (CH_2 sym) and 2 920 cm^{-1} (CH_2 sym.); δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.3 (6H, t, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.4 (4H, q, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$) and 8.1 (8H, m, ArH).

p,p'-Dihydrazinocarbonyl diphenylsulphone (3): An aqueous solution of hydrazine hydrate (10 ml; 80%) was added to a suspension of 2 (6.7 g, 0.02 mol) in ethanol (30 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h, then cooled to room temperature and poured in ice-water. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (4.2 g, 68%), m.p. 248° (Found: N, 16.71. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires: N, 16.77%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 155 and 1 290 cm^{-1} (S=O asym. and sym.), 1 660 (C=O) and 3 300 cm^{-1} (NH or NH_2); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.6 (4H, s, NHNH_2), 8.2–7.5 (8H, m, ArH) and 10.02 (2H, s, CONH).

p,p'-Bis(2-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)diphenylsulphone (4): A mixture of 3 (3.34 g, 0.01 mol), benzoic acid (2.44 g, 0.02 mol) and phosphorous